

Math Survey 2025

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Abstract

This paper describes new, mostly matrix based algorithms for a recent cluster of extraordinary results that belong to six distinct branches of mathematics. These results are inter-connected in a complicated multi-dimensional web of dependencies. Our earliest paper deals with fractional ordinary differential equations and the proportional sectioning method that accelerates FDE terminal value problems by factors of around 8 to 12 and speeds up many engineering applications.

The new unitary block-decomposition method for all real or complex square matrices $A_{n,n}$ or matrix flows $A(t)_{n,n}$ offers new tools for abandoned and unsolved central Quantum Theory questions that have lain unsolved for a century and can be solved now using Johnson's associated hermitean matrix flow $F(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K$ for the hermitean and skew parts H and K of A . This whole cluster of pure and applied research was inspired by a century old and previously unsolved quantum physics problem that now can be solved by using the hermitean Johnson $F(t)$ function from Field of Values studies in conjunction with the predictive neural network of Yunong Zhang and a threshold based combinatorial 0-1 matrix computational algorithm.

In quantum physics terms our solution makes the assessment of our Chemical Element Tables finally possible after 100 + years of not knowing.

All computational methods in this cluster are conditionally stable. They all give us highly accurate results such as in our adapted ZNN method for matrix flows $A(t)$ or static matrices A that – for example – find nonsingular static matrix symmetrizers with small condition numbers for the first time.

Likewise for the unitary block diagonalisation of many problematic eigenvalue examples that are listed in Matlab's 'Gallery'.

The latter was not suspected or known before.

Predictive Zhang Neural Networks and their seven step set-up process leads to many new solution methods for matrix method when combined with a matrix based threshold algorithm and the unitary block-diagonalisation of square matrices and matrix flows. This is a new unitarily invariant matrix normal form whose qualities have not been studied.

Keywords : math history, numerical analysis, fractional ODEs, shooting methods, proportional sectioning, Linear algebra, unitary block-decomposition, invariant subspace theory, quantum physics, time-varying matrix problem, conditionally stable algorithm, Johnson matrix flow, neural network, zeroing neural network, discretized ZNN algorithm, field of values, matrix flows, matrix normal form, time-varying numerical algorithm, predictive numerical method, matrix symmetrizer, threshold based matrix algorithm, combinatorial 0-1 matrix computational algorithm

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Talk Slides at

<https://webhome.auburn.edu/~uhligfd/MathSurvey2025.pdf>

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0 : A Prolog in Mathematics' History

The cluster of my works in the early 2020s began with investigating the early appearances of the concept behind and the actual term of "Matrix Fields of Values" in the math literature and history.

Otto Toeplitz in Berlin and Felix Hausdorff in Kiel were the first mathematicians to conceive of and introduce this term into our math literature. Toeplitz approached this topic at the Berlin Academy in 1902, when a student there, and coined the term "Wertbereich" in 1918 in front of the Academy in an invited talk for his Habilitation.

The mathematical language at the time had no such 'Field of Values' like terms or words. In Toeplitz mind these concepts slowly originated from theoretical matrix and convexity computational ideas as he wanted to plot the boundary curve of that mathematical 'item' concretely.

Another approach of this subject originated in the study of multi-centuries (or even millennia) of operator polynomials in Linear Functions in infinite dimensional normed vector spaces and what we now call Banach spaces. These studies eventually morphed into Functional Analysis in the mid 1900s. A deep knowledge of these works was applied by Felix Hausdorff in Kiel to n dimensional vector sets under Linear Transformations and this lead to understanding the convexity of the Field of Values for all real or complex square matrices.

The mathematics that surround the historic matrix Field of Values genesis from around 1902 to 1918 are very well explained at the start of Fejér's paper [14] and in Isabelle Bensimon and Kalin Kostadinov's introduction [2].

Henry Minkowski's convex body theorem and proof from around 1900 for $n = 2$ is equally important for understanding the roots of Matrix Fields of Values.

These convexity results were eventually applied to the images of n -vectors in \mathbb{R}^2 that were generated by the Field of Values construct to find interior and boundary FoV points. The field of values boundary points were then standardly (and theoretically, of course) obtained from the extreme eigenvalue eigenvectors x of $A_{n,n}$ after 'evaluating' the Rayleigh quotient $x^* A^* Ax / x^* x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, in the 2-D range plane.

A detailed look at the Field of Values boundary theory from Henri Minkowski's Convex Body theory is offered by Daniel Comeaux in [2]. The works of Constantin Carathéodory [4, 5], Leopold Fejér [13, 14] and Ernst Steinitz [36] influenced both Otto Toeplitz' and Felix Hausdorff's subsequent works [39, 41, 40, 42] and [20] on the 'theoretical' construction of Matrix Field of Values.

All of these works lay the groundwork for Charlie Johnson's final practical computational method for drawing of the Field of Values boundary curve in [24], when effective and accurate matrix eigen-computations had become available in Matrix Numerical Analysis by using John G. F. Francis' QR algorithm [15, 16, 18] and reliable LAPACK codes, in and after the mid 1970s.

300 years ago and more, the relation between the coefficients of various short power series such as Taylor Series, Fourier Series or of algebraic polynomials were scrutinized for their function or mapping properties:

Which early power series snippets thereof could or would likely create poles or blow-ups in the full power series and which power series would transfer compact sets of leading power series coefficients into compact sets in their range space, for example. Such questions on compactness, closedness and finally on convexity were all intertwined abstractly; since Descartes' or Cardano's times and possibly much earlier, beginning with or before Archimedes, and his predecessors in antiquity, – and all around the globe.

These studies all involved concepts in algebra and geometry, analysis and topology, number theory, and the words followed later. Eventually nascent Matrix Theory was involved here after Seki, Leibniz, Cauchy, Gauss, Sylvester, Weierstrass and many others and their contributions, from 1600 through the 1800s.

And Matrix Theory, Matrix Computations and Matrix Applications have grown ever since and are still growing today.

Such mathematical efforts had many applications elsewhere, especially in the expanding engineering work of the beginning Industrial Revolution in the mid 1700s and the 1800s in Europe, and likewise in the second half of the last century for our Engineering needs and advances. And so forth, today and tomorrow – for our ever growing human needs and desires, see [9, 10, 57] for modern applied math examples.

One question of whether or which leading power series 'snippets' could or would create points in their range space in which the line between any two image points would consist entirely of image points or whether there could be gaps where the connection line between two image points was "granular" with some gaps in connectiveness. These were popular topics then at the Academies of the early 1800. But math journals had not been started yet, except for Crelle's and various hand written Academy Reports in Paris, Berlin etc, and it is hard today to find exact references of who did what and when then.

Historically, these developments lead mathematicians to the notions of the closedness of sets, then to compact sets and their preservation under continuous maps, and to the concept of convexity and the desire to preserve some properties under 'power series snippet mappings'. If the input domain lay in certain ways in its space, what was the smallest range that would contain all snippet images and so forth.

By 1900, one could begin to see some future developments of Field of Values properties and of the Field of Values boundary curve as objects of study and concern themselves.

The inventors of the Field of Values (FoV) term, Otto Toeplitz and Felix Hausdorff, built their work on many earlier generations that culminated in Henry Minkowski's "kleinste konvexe Bereiche" studies and his books, his papers and lectures.

Here we quote four papers by Otto Toeplitz from 1902 through 1918, the latter of which suddenly shows how Minkowski and Fejér's and others' work on 'power series snippet mappings' applies directly to the Matrix Field of Values question.

Otto Toeplitz had studied the FoV by developing and using mainly Matrix Theory language and concepts, see his doctoral thesis of 1902 [39] which still looks very modern today. Toeplitz eventually proved in 1918 [42] that the line segment of any two F0V points contains only FoV points and that the FoV points were always connected and filled the connecting set of points in the range space.

Felix Hausdorff approached the FoV problem differently, namely from his knowledge of the multidimensional or infinite dimensional domain extension of Minkowski et al's finite dimensional domain. Felix Hausdorff started with vectors in \mathbb{R}^n or \mathbb{C}^n and n by n matrices. Then he used the field of value boundary point generating algorithm as his mapping between vectors in \mathbb{R}^n or \mathbb{C}^n and our 2-D plotting plane, see [20].

Thus we learned from both almost simultaneously in 1918 that the Field of Values of every square matrix is convex.

These historic algebraic and analytic, and topological and geometric results paved the way for our modern numerical Fields of Values studies and their use in applications from the 1960s through today. They are built on software, computers, and numerical computations.

How to actually compute the Field of Values boundary curve numerically was introduced and studied by Charlie Johnson [23, 24] and others only after the invention of computers and the development of reliable mathematical software from the 1940s into the 1970s.

1 : An Introduction to a Cluster of Recent fundamental Mathematics Results

New Results from the early 2020s that are all interconnected, some of which date back a hundred or more years and which all hinge on new branches and new parts of Matrix Theory and Matrix Computations that were developed by the Author; and helped along by many others.

For general complex or real 1-parameter matrix flows $A(t)_{n,n}$ or for static matrices $A \in \mathbb{C}^{n,n}$, this paper considers ways to block-decompose matrix flows $A(t)_{n,n}$ or single matrices $A_{n,n}$ globally via one constant matrix similarity $C_{n,n}$. Many of its results hinge on this new unitary block diagonalisation algorithm, where

$$A(t) = C^{-1} \cdot \text{diag}(A_1(t), \dots, A_\ell(t)) \cdot C \tag{X}$$

or

$$A = C^{-1} \cdot \text{diag}(A_1, \dots, A_\ell) \cdot C \tag{XX}$$

Here each diagonal block $A_k(t)$ or A_k is square and their number ℓ exceeds 1 – if this is possible, and — if A or $A(t)$ are actually unitarily block-diagonalisable.

The theory and ideas behind our new computational matrix algorithm is elementary and uses the concept of invariant subspaces for Matlab's `eig` computed 'eigenvectors' of a flow matrix $A(t_a)$ and a new combinatorial logic 0-1 algorithm to find the coarsest simultaneous block structure for all other flow matrices $A(t_b)$ for $t_b \neq t_a$ if such a proper unitary block-decomposition exists.

And consequently the algorithm block-diagonalizes any given matrix flow $A(t)$ or any given static matrix A – as finely as possible.

Our new method works efficiently in $O(n^{2.5})$ time for all square matrices $A_{n,n}$ and all square time-varying matrix flows $A(t)$, be they real or complex, normal, with Jordan structures or repeated eigenvalues, and differentiable, continuous, or discontinuous.

Our intended aim is to discover unitarily diagonal-block decomposable matrices and matrix flows as they might originate in real-time from time-varying sensor data.

For unitarily block-diagonalisable n by n A or $A(t)$, the complexity of their numerical treatment decreases swiftly for $O(n^3)$ matrix processes when adopting ‘divide and conquer’ methods on each of their diagonal blocks separately.

The Proof : The Unitary Block-Decompositions and Fast and Accurate Field of Values Boundary Computations of all Square Matrices

The unitary block decomposition of matrix flows or single square matrices has never been resolved by algebraic means in 100 + years and it has possibly never even been tried, because there existed no algebraic way or ideas to start from – before the advent of computers and matrix based software such as Matlab, Mathematica, Octave etc..

Instead, our new way of testing and establishing unitary decomposability of a matrix $A_{n,n}$ or matrix flow $A(t)_{n,n}$ hinges entirely on a threshold based numerical algorithm that decides the issue depending on the lay of the near zero entries and of the sizable ones in the associated hermitean Johnson matrix flow

$$\mathcal{F}(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K \quad (\text{XXX})$$

for $0 \leq t \leq 2\pi$ and $H = (A + A^*)/2$ and $K = (A - A^*)/2i$, the hermitean and skew hermitean parts of $A_{n,n}$.

[For simplicity of presentation, we assume that all matrices A and matrix flows $A(t)$ are real in this paper. Everything is similarly true for complex matrices]

Our block-diagonalizing Algorithm uses the Francis QR eigenvalue method to find the block-diagonal structure of one hermitean Johnson flow matrix $\mathcal{F}(t)$.

But the algorithm operates completely differently from Francis hermitean QR and constructs

a new, previously unknown and *totally different matrix normal form* .

Matrix normal forms generally try to *represent a linear transform as simply as possible* in an appropriate basis.

Francis QR starts from a Hessenberg form for the given matrix A and it tries to upper triangularize A with its 'eigenvalues' appearing on the diagonal and small fill-in in the rest of the upper triangle – if possible.

(Complex eigen-pairs will become 2-dimensional diagonal blocks in QR with a wild upper triangle elsewhere.)

Unfortunately, some complicated eigenstructures for A with repeated eigenvalues or with eigenvalues and principal values cannot be found reliably using Francis QR.

Besides, QR can only work on one matrix A at a time and it can not be used for matrix flows $A(t)$. But it is still our workhorse for eigen questions today.

The accelerating diagonal shifts of Francis QR finally render an upper diagonal matrix under a complicated matrix similarity with A 's 'eigenvalues' *generally* appearing on the 'diagonal'.

Our unitary block-diagonalization algorithm instead creates a block diagonal normal form for all square matrices A and all matrix flows $A(t)$, real or complex. The sizes of the diagonal blocks always depend on a user chosen error threshold.

Our new algorithm computes a block-diagonal matrix structure $diag(A_1, \dots, A_\ell)$ or $diag(A_1(t), \dots, A_\ell(t))$ for any static square matrix A or any matrix flow $A(t)$ with a clear all zero upper right block matrix and a clear all zero lower left block matrix and it does so with one similarity $C^{-1} \dots C$ as was described in formulas (X) and (XX) earlier.

Many uses have been developed for the backward-stable Francis QR algorithm over time while the potential of the conditionally-stable unitary block-diagonalisation algorithm has not been studied nor developed yet.

Some early applications such as solving a still open Quantum Physics problem from the 1920s or the nonsingular matrix symmetrizer problem will be explained in more detail later on in this paper.

The unitary block diagonalisation algorithm might show its worth in higher dimensional matrix problems such as for Tensor Flows, where it might become useful in photographic studies of digitized images and in image restoration, as well as in image authentication and forensic studies of image manipulations, see [57] for example.

One just cannot tell its true potential; it is all too soon ...

Our block-diagonalisation algorithm starts from two Johnson flow matrices $\mathcal{F}(t_1)$ and $\mathcal{F}(t_2)$ that are linearly independent. Then we form the 0-1 logic matrices $Flogic(t_1)$ and $Flogic(t_2)$ in Matlab's `spy` function and assemble the normalized eigenvectors of $\mathcal{F}(t_1)$ combinatorially in $V'(t_1)$ (the V hermitean transpose) so that adjacent rows in $Flogic(t_1)$ have equal 0 and 1 patterned blocks, if possible.

Next we reorder the rows of $Flogic(t_2)$ so that they have the same 0-1 pattern as $Flogic(t_1)$ (if possible) and then continue the block-diagonalization process with logic 0-1 matrices only. Our logic 0-1 pattern matrix algorithms all use a simple logic combinatorial algorithm that establishes and refines a joint proper unitary block decomposition of both logic 0-1 `spy` pattern matrices $Flogic(t_1)$ and $Flogic(t_2)$ very quickly, if that is possible; see [53] through [56].

To prove the main Unitary Diagonability Theorem [54], we assume that for any matrix $A_{n,n}$ the hermitean Johnson flow $\mathcal{F}(t)$ contains two linearly independent matrices $\mathcal{F}(t_a) \neq \mathcal{F}(t_b)$ where $\mathcal{F}(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K$ for the hermitean and skew parts of $A_{n,n}$.

Going down from the top block leads to a joint unitary block diagonal structure for all $\mathcal{F}(t)$ with $t \in [0, 2\pi]$. Since $\mathcal{F}(0) = H$ and $\mathcal{F}(\pi/2) = K$, the matrix A or the flow $A(t)$ have the same unitary block structure as the hermitean matrices $\mathcal{F}(t_1)$ and $V(t_2)$ do, and our algorithm is complete.

What is going on here? To begin this section, we had stipulated that for simplicity that we were only going to deal with real matrices A and real matrix flows $A(t)$ here, see Equation (XXX) above.

Why would we talk of 'hermitean matrices' here where symmetric ones would suffice? How do we best designate real matrix transposes, by A^T , A' , or $A^t(t)$ in Matlab.

This notational quandary depends on the context. And I am not repeating every block-diagonalisation result or statement here with referring to both cases of over \mathbb{R} or over \mathbb{C} .

This algorithm depends, however, on the magnitude relations between the non-zero entries and the near zero entries in $\mathcal{F}(t_i)$ for $i = 1, 2$ and a threshold.

If the chosen threshold is too small there might be no discernible block structure at all and if it is too large, then the block-diagonal structure might only show the non-zero entries on the diagonal of the computed block-diagonal matrix.

To distinguish between computed entries as being 'zero' or definitely 'nonzero' is a an uncharted question. For the moment we have set the 'zero' threshold heuristically to

$$\|A\|_{fro} \cdot 10^{-13} \approx \|A\|_{fro} \cdot eps$$

when working in double precision with machine constant $eps \approx 2.2 \cdot 10^{-16}$ in Matlab.

We repeat : Our constructive numerical proof hinges on an algorithm to distinguish between the near zero entries and the definitely non-zero entries of a matrix accurately and reliably.

We know of no way to prove the unitary block-diagonalization theorem algebraically. Our numerical proof depends on an appropriate size for its 'near zero' threshold.

An algebraic proof of our result was never attempted. We dare to claim that an algorithmic proof was impossible before the advent of computers and a deeper understanding of matrix flows such as the hermitean Johnson flow $\mathcal{F}(t)$ and the predictive qualities and high accuracy of Zhang Neural Networks as brought to light recently in ZNN [60] and AZNN [58].

The ability to construct the field of values $\mathcal{F}(A)$ boundary curve of some unitarily decomposable matrices quickly and accurately via shooting methods led to recent further studies of matrix eigencurve behavior by many authors who tried to locate their crossings or hyperbolic avoidances thereof that had first appeared in original Quantum Physics studies by von Neumann and Paul Wigner [32, p. 469], in Copenhagen, in Berlin, and in Göttingen; in the 1920s.

Albert Einstein shunned this fundamental Quantum Theory problem and rather worked on relativity. Niels Bohr's group wanted to understand eigencurve crossings and their relation to the unitary matrix block-decomposability of matrices, but neither succeeded.

Eigencurve crossing studies for the still un-resolved unitary block-diagonalisation problem would begin anew with Charlie Johnson's work [23, 24] on the field of values in the 1970s and pick up again in the 1990s in Luca Dieci et al.'s papers [7, 8] and in many other papers of Luca's research group, and by others; and in Sébastien Loisel and Peter Maxwell's paper [27], and in some of my eigencurve papers such as in [51], [53], [54], and [61].

This development continued until around 2020, when several small partial results (maybe 15 %) of the unitary block-decomposition problem had been solved, but no complete classification had been found and the century old problems with eigencurve crossings were still open in 2023 until [54] appeared in print.

My final classification of unitary block-decompositions [54] for both, general matrix flows and static matrices, was ultimately inspired by Yunong Zhang's parameter-varying Neural Networks that date back to his doctoral thesis [67] of 2001.

These recent results are all inter-woven and they all have contributed to each other's solutions and to the author's understanding of this cluster's six interconnected new fundamental computational results and finding their proofs.

Each of the new results has advanced its area tremendously where no math methods had been found for decades or longer, by researchers that used our standard analytical or algebraic mathematical or computational approaches.

The mathematical process that obtained these results was never predictable – until everything fell into place in 2023/24, was mathematically sound, proved and these papers were quickly accepted and printed.

The conditionally stable Matrix Computational algorithms of this research cluster do not solve any nearby problem accurately – as *backward stable* methods are designed to do.

Instead, these new methods deliver highly accurate results at high speed and they do not suffer from the high inaccuracies in the traditional 'backward stable' fashion that we are accustomed to today.

Conditionally stable algorithms were often shunned by the numerical analysis community, see the fate of [17] from 2008 for example. The reports on this paper by the editor and the four referee reports dealt with the questionable usefulness and quality of its theoretical and numerical matrix methods.

More specifically the reports asserted that we had not used 'stable methods', meaning "backwards stable methods", but instead, we had used Cleve Moler's (stable !) Matlab m-files in place of John Francis' 'stable' QR eigenvalue algorithm and the fully compiled 'backward stable' LAPACK codes.

(In our "numerical computations", ugh !)

Our new methods can all encounter rare breakdowns that are easily bypassed and when bypassed, they give us near exact results in the end, see [58], e. g. .

Adapted ZNN [58] has solved the open and previously unsolvable matrix symmetrizer problem in [11] where we were unable to find invertible matrix symmetrizers by using John Francis' QR [15, 16], Gene Golub and Velvel Kahan's SVD [19] and optimization algorithms and more, but failed to find nonsingular symmetric matrix factorizations $\hat{S} \cdot A = T$ with real A , symmetric $T = T'$, and a nonsingular symmetric matrix \hat{S} , see [38], in our all-out effort for matrices with repeated eigenvalues or difficult Jordan structures from Matlab's 'Gallery'.

Next we will highlight some of the supporting and resulting Theorems and Matrix Algorithms of this research cluster.

We start with

(a) ZNN

Zhang Neural Networks for matrix problems were invented two decades ago, see [67].

Their workings are explained in detail for discretized matrix problems in [60]. Today they are used extensively in robot control and other modern engineering problems that need real-time predictive and accurate solutions.

[60] explains their workings in 7 steps for many standard single parameter matrix processes.

Discretized ZNN starts from an error equation $e(t)$ at time t .

$$(1) \quad e(t) = \text{exact solution} - \text{computed solution at time } t .$$

Convergence of ZNN is assured by stipulating that the error decreases exponentially in t , i.e.,

$$(2) \quad \dot{e}(t) = -\alpha \cdot e(t) \quad \text{for } \alpha > 0.$$

Then users (3) have to solve this ODE algebraically for $\dot{e}(t)$, which may be impossible. If impossible, the error function has to be expressed differently or a more involved problem set-up may be needed, see [60] for such occurrences.

Zhang Neural Networks rely on convergent parametrized 1-step ahead finite

$$(4) \quad \text{difference formulas.}$$

In [52] we have constructed several convergent look-ahead formulas using the forward Taylor expansion of $e(t)$. See [64] for another method to develop convergent 1-step ahead finite difference formulas with rational coefficients.

After (5) choosing one predictive formula from the list in [52] according to the desired error order, and

(6) equating the expressions for $\dot{e}(t_{k+1})$ in (3) and (5), simply solve the resulting derivative free equation for the future solution $x(t_{k+1})$ at time t_{k+1} .

And in (7) we iterate the process.

(b) Adapted ZNN

Time-varying adapted Zhang Neural Networks can compute well conditioned nonsingular symmetrizers for static matrices. They supersede all 'backward stable' standard methods such as QR, SVD, or optimization methods as shown in [11] where these methods all failed to give us well conditioned symmetrizers much of the time. The adapted ZNN method is extremely accurate down to errors in the 10^{-18} range, but it is only 'conditionally stable'.

The adapted ZNN method of [58] studies the effects of varying the decay constant η in the error function ODE over time and of changing the ZNN finite difference formula used in different stages of the iterations, as well as adapting the unstable simple Euler iteration to achieve a quicker error decay at start-up.

With an appropriately adapted AZNN method, see [58], we were able to compute nonsingular matrix symmetrizers $S = S^T$ with $S \cdot A = T$ and $A = S^{-1} \cdot T$ for $T = T^T$ for all square matrices A with symmetrizing errors generally less than Matlab's `eps` and with very small condition numbers for stable invertibility of S . This was generally impossible before with standard matrix methods; see [11, Section 4].

(c) Plotting the Boundary Curve of the Field of Values

The field of values of a matrix (FOV) has been studied by Toeplitz [42] since 1910 and also by Haussdorf [20] in 1919 as a means to estimate the eigenvalues of matrices. In 1978, Johnson [24] proposed to plot the FOV boundary of matrices using the hermitean matrix flow

$$\mathcal{F}(t) = \cos(t)H + \sin(t)K \quad (= (F(t))^*)$$

for the hermitean part $H = (A + A^*)/2 = H^*$ and the skew hermitean part

$$K = (A - A^*)/(2i) = K^* \quad \text{of } A_{n,n} \text{ for } t \in [0, 2\pi] .$$

And then plotting both real extreme eigenvalues of the hermitean matrices $\mathcal{F}(t)$ in the rotated plane via the quadratic form x^*Ax/x^*x ; for details see [24] .

This idea was adapted by Loisel and Maxwell in [27] into a path following ODE for the slope of $\mathcal{F}(t)$ that bested Johnson's algorithm [24] in run time and accuracy. And ZNN was finally adopted to the FOV problem for even better results in [58] .

Today ZNN path following is the best method available for the matrix FOV boundary curve problem.

ZNN is designed for general square matrices or matrix flows, real or complex, and it should be combined with the unitary block-diagonalizing result of [54], see subsections (d) and (e) below, for additional speed-up.

(d) Eigencurves

My earlier research [49, 50, 53] on eigencurve behavior lead directly to this cluster’s centerpiece in part (e), i.e., the numerical discovery of the finest block-diagonal structure for general square matrices $A_{n,n}$ or matrix flows $A_{n,n}(t)$ by unitary similarity in [54] .

Sébastien Loisel and Peter Maxwell [27] had tested their fast ODE path following FOV method in 2018 on block diagonal matrices and noted that eigencurve crossings for the maximal eigenvalue created unsolvable havoc for block diagonal matrix flows with overlapping block spectra.

Likewise, Luca Dieci and multiple co-authors, see [7, 8] for example, had worked on the eigencurve crossing problem for 20 years and could not succeed to plot FOVs of general unitarily block diagonalisable matrices. Their eigencurve crossings research and methods were seemingly abandoned around 2020 with no way for algebraic proofs or computational algorithms.

This quest had been started in Quantum Physics about a century ago by von Neumann, Friedrich Herman Hund and Eugene Paul Wigner, see [32], [22] and their graphical depiction of eigencurve crossings below.

Drawing of 'eigencurve crossings' and their hyperbolic avoidance from [32, p. 469] and [22]. Curve β_1 crosses E_2 and E_1 and avoids β_2 . Curve β_2 crosses only E_1 and avoids all other curves in a hyperbolic way.

I had become interested in the eigencurve crossing problem in [53, 54] and this has led me to discover a solution to the century old unitary block diagonalization problem for matrices in [54] – after I had understood Johnson’s $\mathcal{F}(t)$ function and ZNN iterations more deeply.

Many fundamental Linear Algebra insights from the classical 19th century and from the modern computational era from the 1930s on were equally important for the inter-twining results of this presentation.

I have described the history of our area in mathematics in detail to keep us aware of the importance and value of all of it that was discovered eons ago and recently.

We need to be conscious of math history and cherish all of it today.

(e) Faster Computational Methods for Unitarily Decomposable Matrices

Of special interest here are square matrices with involved Jordan structures and with any (previously unknown) unitary block diagonalizabilities.

To our surprise, about one quarter of the matrices in Matlab’s ‘Gallery’ with difficult eigen-structures are block diagonalizable. This had not been known or even thought about before because there had been no appropriate tools for a hundred and more years.

Checking for unitary block-diagonalizability before working on many matrices of the same kind will shorten computational run times greatly, as shown extensively in the AZNN paper [58, Sections 2, 3.1 and 3.2, Figures 1 through 14 and Tables 1 and 2].

Structured sparse matrices such as Toeplitz, Hankel, Circulant and other striped matrices from finite difference methods for boundary value problems come to mind here as well. Figure 6 in [58] explains the high benefits of even relatively large maximal block sizes for speeding up unitarily block-diagonalisable matrix computations.

The long term behavior of ZNN methods for time-varying real matrix square roots for example, shows an ever downward decreasing exponentially decaying error function, see [58, Figure 1]. With properly chosen AZNN parameters, after around 16 minutes the error size of time-varying matrix square roots generally decrease smoothly into the 10^{-18} or lower error range.

Eventually small computational rounding errors of AZNN led to matrix square roots with negative 'entries' and the computed matrix iterates would then bifurcate, with some test matrix entries becoming complex conjugate pairs. These would stay non-real until the matrix square root entries became all real again. Then the complex bifurcation would end and all would stay real for a while in the sub-sub 10^{-18} range, with a continually decreasing error function. See [58].

There are several open questions here on the behavior of time-varying discretized ZNN methods. How can one connect the error threshold of the machine constant with incoming ZNN data and uniformly restart the ZNN process if needed. Recall that well conditioned symmetrizers of static matrices were computed by AZNN with errors well below 10^{-18} .

Our evidence suggests that it is detrimental to run time-varying ZNN or AZNN for durations exceeding 16 or 18 minutes in double precision computations and therefore into the exponential decay problem zone. Such as for matrix square roots after some 40,000 iteration steps (and more than 2 hours of simulated runtime) when using time-varying ZNN at the 50Hz standard clock rate $\tau = 0.02$ sec here for example, see [58, Figure 1].

We generally advise to restart the process well before the 'errors' have become smaller than the floating point machine constant $\epsilon \sim 10^{-16}$ in Matlab ZNN or AZNN computations.

(f) The Proportional Secting Method for Fractional Differential equations

This section seems peripheral mathematically to our earlier mathematical research cluster, but its results and methods are central to much of Mathematics once we appreciate its Applications in Modern Engineering; and central to this work.

The paper [10] by Kai Diethelm and Frank Uhlig originated after a zoom talk by Kai on fractional differential equations (FDEs) on the Irish Numerical Analysis Forum INA zoom talks in 2021. Frank contacted Kai about the selection of shooting points to start the FDE iterations and otherwise he suggested to continue the numerical methods that were then commonly used in this area.

Fractional derivatives occur naturally in FDE systems when non-local effects are present in the physical model. Here ‘non-local’ may refer to both time or space variables. This typically happens in mathematical models if the properties of a material exhibit memory dependent behavior changes such as with viscoelastic materials, in fracking simulations and so forth.

Only a few efficient methods are generally used to solve initial value problems for FDEs and these are mostly concerned with optimizing their step sizes. In practical terms, this section rounds out our earlier cut-off polynomial or power series approach to convexity, compactness and the like in the development of the early 1900s and in the theoretic Field of Values problem for matrices.

The fractional differential problems and algorithms go back to Goesta Magnus Mittag-Leffler [29, 30, 31] in the early 1900s. These were recently used, expanded upon and described by Ronald L. Bagey, by Michelle Caputo, by YangQuan Chen, by Neville Ford, by Allen D. Freed, by Roberto Garrappa, by Rudolf Gorenflo, by Christian Lubich, by Mark M. Maerschaert, by Francesco Mainardi, by Igor Podlubny, by Arnold Ross, by Peter J. Torvik, by Hoang The Tuan, and by Kai Diethelm and myself, and by their and our students and collaborators, and by many many others around the globe.

For details refer to the text and the References in [10], then look at the comparison images in [57] on p. 12, at the runtime data on p. 15 and 19, and at the proofs in two appendices, p. 21 - 31 of [57]. The new matrix based method [57], applied for fractional ODEs, uses only simple problem specific Matrix Arithmetic and does not enter into Tensor methods for image restoration or authentication and therefore works around 3 times faster than the standard methods for image analysis. The standard methods generally always use fractional versions of collocation methods, such as Adams-Bashforth ODE integrators, backward differentiation formulas, or other linear multistep methods.

These ODE solvers are the workhorse computational building blocks that take up most of their CPU runtime. They are generally combined with classical bisection which can only halve the feasible shooting points interval in each step.

Note that the first search interval can be astronomically large and complicated as the classical estimation techniques for the starting interval points bounds often require us to evaluate Mittag-Leffler functions with large positive arguments. When containment intervals with upper bounds of around 10^7 units occur on one side of the 'correct shooting start', and with just 2 units on the other side, the classical bisection methods will iterate dozens of times and only halve the search interval's size, slowly step by step.

The book by Keith Oldham and Jerome Spanier [33] is a good starting point for the area of Fractional Difference ODEs, as is the survey article on Matrix Mittag-Leffler Functions and Numerical Computations thereof by Marina Popolizio [34].

We have started in Section 1 with studying the genesis of the Field of Values and exploring its roots in antiquity and now end this paper with some of the most technical Modern Matrix Computations of 'snippet' matrix behavior in Applied Math and cutting edge Engineering Applications. Two bookends of sorts for this survey paper and a good way to conclude it, I hope.

The result in [10] is an extraordinary advance. The Proportional Secting Method (PSM) uses around 1/10th of the bisection method iterations; from fracking calculations to Elon Musk's way of returning space craft to earth., and on and on. It gets done in around 1/10th of the standard shooting methods' CPU time for Fractional ODEs. When joined by predictive ZNN, PSM can solve FDEs in real time.

Today Fractional ODEs appear in many Engineering Problems and serve in multiple Applications. Their solution methods are indispensable today as a computational backbone of our Modern Life, Engineering, and Industry.

The Proportional Secting method is simple to implement. It always uses the latest two starting points to determine the next shooting start, except for the first iteration that is (at this moment) still determined via Mittag-Leffler [29, 30, 31] estimates.

Efforts to dismiss all Mittag-Leffler type evaluations in the accelerated computational FDE solvers of [10] are under way.

The proportional secting iterates are computed without any logical "if" loops or interval containment requirements. Thus it is much faster in reducing Mittag-Leffler based or other initial shooting intervals via Proportional Secting.

At the time of our investigations in [10], some of the FDE shooters were exploring the effects of using low accuracy solution at the beginning of the FDE integration process and other speed-up ideas. These improvements would sometimes reduce their relatively large total iterations counts by 1 or 2 steps or increase them similarly, but not by 90 % as Proportional Secting in [10] does.

Reasons for this behavior of the 'classical' bisection based FDE solvers were debated and never found. And the future direction for developing new FDE solvers was stuck in limbo – until [10] appeared; which ended these efforts graciously.

My bad ... , creating math unemployment ...

This is the end of my math talk
with selections from a new
extraordinary rich
Mathematical Research Cluster.

This paper touches two separate areas, in full detail dealing with
fundamental mathematical research and glancingly on modern
Math Education.

The main first part has described recent mathematical advances.

A second separate companion paper [63] addresses our elemen-
tary Linear Algebra teachings and deals with the globe-wide prob-
lem of "teaching for the test", mostly in 'top-down' lecturing, –
only glancingly at our most urgent problem in Mathematics today.

We are generally not conveying Linear Algebra through interac-
tive teaching methods, nor introducing modern Matrix Theory
and Matrix Computational methods. To our beginning students
– not at all.

This dilemma is our most urgent task for Mathematics

Today .

Are there any problems in our Linear Algebra teaching or teachings ?

In subjects taught or ... where are our problems – if any ?

In Linear Algebra and Matrix Theory, what is wrong ?

Teaching and/or research wise ?

What needs to be done immediately ?

We must modernize our early College syllabi in Linear Algebra and enliven this area of Mathematics that helps us all so extraordinarily in our daily cell-phone and internet based lives and in our AI and engineering advances.

How do we, how do you mostly teach beginners' Linear Algebra classes today?

Which subjects do we, you, and I teach?

Using modern Matrix Theory based ideas or from a classical and algebraic standpoint ?

Top-down taught or taught interactively ?

These are our most urgent questions today,

in All of Mathematics .

Postscript :

Amazingly, the Math Subject Classification lists of the Zentralblatt and the AMS both come up totally blank, with no entry, when searching for 'Mittag-Leffler', or 'Neural Network', or the 'Field of Values', for example.

Searching for 'QR' brings up 9 papers with QR in their title, but nothing else.

This paper's research and its underlying fundamental mathematical notions, modern applications, modern computations, and a respect of our entire Math History do not have a place in the Zentralblatt's and AMS'

"Classifications Mathematics Universe" .

Or so it seems. This is a cruel disservice to all branches of Mathematics. That we as Mathematicians now suffer needlessly.

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